

Across Learning Areas: Focus on Digital Narratives of Teachers

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Abstract. The study was conducted to understand and describe the teachers' approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners' comprehension. A qualitative research design was used, and assumptions regarding selecting participants and ethics in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data were considered. Respondents were the Teachers of Integrated Schools. They were purposely selected through referrals and using facilitating questions to draw out narratives on their experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and further learning insights, given their undertakings as technologically inclined teachers. Experiences of teachers found to have been challenged with technical difficulties in accessibility assessment and evaluation. Coping mechanisms have been found to adapt the template and guides, making collaborative learning and professional development possible. Educational insights included a review of policies and guidelines, collaboration and sharing of resources, and coming up with assessment and evaluation criteria. Future direction may provide an opportunity to explore the long-term effects of the coping mechanisms employed by teachers and the effectiveness of the strategies employed in addressing the challenges encountered. Future research can also focus on developing innovative approaches to support teachers in coping with the demands of the new face-to-face modality in the context of newer approaches through digital narratives across learning areas.

KEY WORDS

1. Digital Narratives
2. new face-to-face modality
3. Assessment and Evaluation

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1. Introduction

Information communication technologies (ICT) are not just tools but potential game-changers in education. They are influencing every aspect of human life, from workplaces to entertainment. Many people recognize ICTs as catalysts for transformative change, such as changes in working conditions, handling and exchanging information, teaching methods, learning approaches, scientific research, and accessing information communication technologies. In this digital era, ICT use in the classroom is essential and can potentially revolutionize how students learn and apply the required 21st-century skills. ICT improves teaching and learning, and teachers must perform their role as creators of pedagogical environments. ICT helps a teacher present his teaching attractively and can learn for learners at any level of educational programs. Fostering a culture of digital awareness equips individuals with the vital knowledge and tools necessary to exercise control over their data, enabling them to make

informed decisions regarding its collection, usage, and sharing. Teaching training programs in India are becoming valuable and attractive in ICT (Demirtas, 2020). Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), exemplified by the Internet and interactive multimedia, are an important Integrating Information and Communication Technology, or ICT, into teaching and learning has become a significant concern for educators in developing countries like the Philippines. ICT must be used and taught in powerful and meaningful ways. With its rapid development, educators should find ways to integrate technology into the learning process. ICT should not drive education; educational goals and needs must drive its use in schools. Targeting holistic growth for learners is crucial in realizing the need to develop ICT curriculum standards for K-12 schools in the Philippines. The researcher believes that developing these standards is a decision-making process that will dictate how Filipino students acquire ICT concepts and skills to help them achieve the more significant benefits of learning. Setting standards is a powerful learning tool because it clearly expresses what all learners should know and be able to do. Standards are a common reference tool for the country and provide a defined framework for national testing. Standards focus on developing new ways to organize curriculum content, instructional programs, and assessment plans for schools. Standards will help the teachers design curriculum, instruction, and assessment based on what is essential to learning. They also enable teachers to clarify expectations to students, improving their learning. Importantly, standards set clear performance expectations for students, motivating them to meet the standards and understand the value of their learning (Steiner, 2000).

Instruction integrating ICT in Philippine

schools was created based on learning standards. Curriculum delivery is managed carefully, and the standards to be met are selected and analyzed. Teachers should refer to the targeted skills for each content area and grade level as they plan and implement their classroom activities. Instructional activities and assessments are to be selected and designed so that students can demonstrate mastery of standards (Rudenko et al., 2020). Currently, Cluster 4 Integrated Schools in Davao City Division upholds the strengthening of ICT integration in the pedagogical strategies among teachers. Researchers have found that using ICT is an effective intervention to increase learners' performance across learning areas. Likewise, ICT integration has been included among strands in classroom observations. Thus, the proponent has to investigate further the significant differences among the approaches to using ICT to test its effectiveness in increasing learners' level of comprehension across learning areas. Thus, this study is conducted. This phenomenological research study aimed to describe the digital narratives that enhance learners' comprehension across learning areas in Cluster 4 Integrated Schools. At this stage in the research, teachers' ICT approaches, given their lived experiences, challenges encountered, and insights, are generally defined as the learners' direction in enhancing comprehension to augment academic performance and ability to develop and improve despite all instructional interventions delivered, and where learning was generally happening not only in school but at home as well as being considered to be explored.

1.1. Research Questions—This study aimed to understand and describe the teachers' approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners' comprehension. It sought to answer to the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the experiences of integrated school teachers in their digital narratives across learning areas?

- (2) How do integrated school teachers cope with the challenges encountered in the approaches through digital narratives across learning areas?
- (3) What educational insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.2. *Purpose of the Study*—The proposed study aimed to determine the significant effect of information and communication technology on learners' level of comprehension during the newer expected delivery of education appreciating the context among Integrated Schools of Cluster 4, Davao City Division. The results of this study will be beneficial and provide significant inputs and bases for the management of curriculum implementation and assessment, given the quality assurance assessment cycle for schools to consider how curriculum policy can be improved. The following stakeholders shall be beneficial given the study's output. School Principals. The School Principal is expected to manage the curriculum implementation of Key Stage 1 on the Grade 1 level to prepare learners and teachers for the skills intended to be mastered given the new regular learning modality. Thus, the study's results provided insights to school heads of Cluster 4 Integrated Schools regarding how ICT approaches could be practical and improve learners' comprehension levels.

Teachers. Teachers assigned in integrated schools experience newer learning environments where elementary and secondary teachers have different orientations in pedagogical practices. In this context, teachers ensure that their efforts to implement and facilitate learners' learning will not be in vain. Thus, the effectiveness and production of outputs through ICT strategic approaches based on objectives and targets set by the MELCs can be achieved. The study's results will give teachers an idea of using ICT as a strategic approach to comprehension and allow them to see if approaches can make teaching more effective and learners become more productive and contribute to their performance development skills. Parents play significant roles in their children's skills

development. The study's results would also give insights and enlightenment to the PTA and the school governing council members, advocating empowerment to continuously improve the school's process and performance and learners' academic achievement through full participation in the whole cycle process. Future Researchers. Implications based on the study's generated results would provide more information to future researchers so they can replicate the practices discovered in the proposed study. These practices include the type and approaches of curriculum implementation and the efficiency elements in improving the quality delivery of education outputs through the process introduced in the MELCs. The following terms were variables used in the study, and definition by concept and operation was presented according to how the terms were used in the study context. This served as the references in the analysis and

Interpret the results to develop meaningful implications for a better understanding and recommendations. Information and Communication Technology Approaches. ICT-enhanced learning promotes a thematic, integrative approach to teaching and learning. This approach eliminates the artificial separation between the disciplines and between theory and practice that characterizes the traditional classroom approach. ICT-enhanced learning was student-directed and diagnostic. In this study, the term is used as the independent variable. UNESCO formulated four approaches to developing ICT in schools: emerging approach, applying approach, integrating approach, and transforming. Learner's Level of Comprehension. Comprehension means understanding text in spoken, written, and visual form. Comprehension is an active and complex process that simultaneously extracts and constructs meaning from text. In

this study, the term is used as the dependent variable, where its indicators are the three levels of comprehension, namely, literal, inferential, and appreciative level of comprehension. These indicators are to be measured to determine the extent of the learner's comprehension given approaches to ICT, which can significantly impact the learner's comprehension.

1.3. Review of Significant Literature—The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has significantly transformed teaching and learning practices across different learning areas. Digital narratives are one such approach, utilizing digital tools like videos, podcasts, blogs, and infographics to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Research indicates that digital narratives help develop critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication skills among students (Casambre et al., 2015; Labastilla Macalinao, 2018).

1.3.1. Challenges in ICT Integration—However, teachers face challenges such as technical difficulties, limited access to resources, and the need for effective assessment strategies. ICT's effectiveness in education relies on teachers' digital literacy and the availability of adequate infrastructure (Rudenko et al., 2021; Hermawan et al., 2017). Accessibility issues further complicate integration, as students and teachers require consistent access to technological resources (Ullah, 2020; Huang, 2022).

1.3.2. Coping Mechanisms—To address these challenges, various coping mechanisms have been proposed, including professional development, collaboration, and the use of templates and guidelines. Professional development helps teachers acquire the necessary skills to implement digital narratives and ICT tools effectively (Smith Colby, 2016; Dimaano, 2020). Collaboration among teachers is vital for sharing resources, strategies, and experiences, thereby enhancing their digital literacy and classroom practices (Jang Chen, 2017; Ho

et al., 2019).

1.3.3. Policy and Guidelines Development—Effective ICT integration also requires clear policies and guidelines that promote equitable access and support pedagogically sound practices. Studies emphasize the need for policies that ensure safe and responsible use of technology while fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Wang, Chen, Liang, 2015; Rivera Aban, 2018).

1.3.4. Assessment and Evaluation—The evaluation of digital narratives requires comprehensive criteria that consider content, creativity, technical quality, and critical thinking (Reinders Wattana, 2016; Fidalgo-Blanco et al., 2018). The use of rubrics has proven effective in providing clear expectations and objective assessments of student outputs (Mendoza Espinosa, 2016; Valdez Tadena, 2018).

1.4. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on modern educational technology theory as espoused by Uno Cygnaeus (1810-1888), the father of Finnish folk schools and pioneer of educational arts and crafts. Cygnaeus developed many teachings connected with industrial life and educational technology. Cygnaeus' goals and comprehensive school evolved with more diverse educational content and a stronger emphasis on creativity. Uno Cygnaeus considered 'technological' content an essential part of craft education. Thanks to Cygnaeus, education for work has been established as a school subject. Today, students are learning handicraft teaching, integrated with Educational Technology, as a part of their general education (Ivanchuk et al., 2020). Given this, modern educational technology theory is a broad and specific concept. It refers to the theory and practice of optimizing teaching with modern technology. Modern educational technology theory is closely related to university-quality education. Technology empowers teachers to develop creative and interactive classrooms and gives them ac-

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

cess to innovative resources. Effective educators understand the benefits of integrating technology in the classroom and finding new ways to make lessons meaningful (Rudenko et al., 2021). As such, integrative learning can take place. This approach involves bringing together prior knowledge and experiences to support new knowledge and experiences. By doing this, learners draw on their skills and apply them to new experiences at a more complex level. Furthermore, this was the process of connecting concepts and experiences to apply information and skills to novel and complex issues or challenges (Galimova Shvetsova, 2016). Digital learning platforms facilitate real-time assessment and feedback, providing immediate insights into students' comprehension and progress. Educators can use data analyt-

ics to identify areas where students need additional support, enabling timely interventions and personalized guidance. Digital literacy allows using technological tools in the learning process, such as e-books, learning videos, simulations, and online learning platforms (Deja et al., 2021). In this study, the context of modern educational technology theory lies in its application through contextualizing information and communication technology approaches to make learning effective, given the estimation of levels of comprehension. As shown in Figure 1, the working themes were the lived experiences of digital natives across learning areas and the challenges they encountered across learning areas, which intersect with the learning insights of digital natives across learning areas.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. As elaborated in this chapter, exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation. This details the operational implementation of the methodology used in the study. The primary sources of the concepts were taken from the respective authors who established the foundation for qualitative research methods. Parts of this chapter were philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, design and procedure, ethical considerations, the role of the researcher, data collection, analysis, framework, and the study's trustworthiness. Each section is thoroughly conceptualized to establish authority and ethical standards in the collection, analysis, and interpretation process. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used for proofreading, as it is a common ethical practice in many articles today. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' histories, perspectives, and experiences, mainly when exploring

sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group's cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented.

Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry that asks, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the BE Coordinators as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, "ultimates," or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. Creswell (2012) pointed out that reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the participants discussed teachers' experiences and their approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners' comprehension. They tried to look into their strategies for addressing the challenges and educational insights. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011), researchers identified phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." This study intended to gather information from the participants or teachers in Cluster 4 Integrated Schools as to how their approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 enhance learners' comprehension. It is assumed that close interaction with the participants was established to

gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and strategies used as approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 to enhance learners' comprehension. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) argues that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretations. Rhetoric means reporting reality through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the researcher would report objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study context, the researcher used the first person to elucidate teachers' experiences as they relate their approaches through digital narratives to enhance learners' comprehension.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the challenges experienced by the integrated school teachers in Cluster 4 in using technological integration across learning areas were gathered through an in-depth interview (IDI), and their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the challenges experienced by Integrated School Teachers in their approaches through technolog-

ical integration and digital narratives became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." Using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the challenges and experiences of Integrated School Teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), stressed that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research is that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge. By analyzing how an event occurs in our daily lives, we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into its nature (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). Using phenomenology, which was concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the challenges experienced and mechanisms used by the Integrated School Teachers were explored. Insights were drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted

with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread, culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher could construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) added that phenomenology, rooted in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also helpful in following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as investigating their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to explore the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Based on Quad's statements (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews are beneficial for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and obtaining in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via extended interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her observations should be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding actions and experiences, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since this study focused on exploring and assessing the teachers' experience and feelings towards approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners' comprehension, the researcher would intend to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of

this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations could be specified as one of the most essential parts of the research. The researcher must adhere to the research aims, impart authentic knowledge and truth, and prevent errors. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was conducted explicitly among Integrated School Teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushed the researcher's interest was the challenges faced by Integrated school teachers in using interactive media instruction in the classroom to ameliorate teaching competence. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants assured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and was based on an understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The informed consent letter aims to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were

required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating. Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents would experience

Potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate. Further, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their natural sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data

findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any communication related to the research should be done honestly. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The respondents accessed the results of the study heads of the participating schools because the information was available and was placed on CDs or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she was qualified to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to ensure that the study could be completed successfully within the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions

and recommendations for improving it. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study's conduct. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.5. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions would lead to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were Eight (8) teachers from Integrated

Schools of Cluster 4, Division of Davao City. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least five years; (2) elementary school teacher; and (3) experienced in technology-integrative teaching. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducted interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. The researcher interpreted ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio or video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher

are correctly secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was safeguarding participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensures that the findings are accurate for the participants and that their voices are heard. The researcher organizes and presents data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The study's findings are presented through research questions, stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity admits the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings to implement non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed.

Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. The researcher asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in asking permission to conduct the study. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the

study in the identified school. The researcher will send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapters 1 and 2 and the research instrument, explaining the study's objectives and the participants' identification. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before conducting it. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher precisely transcribed the interviewees' responses by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data were then categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data was compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing. The body of data was then compared and contrasted between the participants to identify patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the participants' answers from the interviews using

Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a significant idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher employed environmental triangulation. It was a technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the

findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which factors influence the information received; these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature.

2.9. Analytical Framework—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. The gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes in the analysis stage. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher would become aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and make a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may be unable to review all the mate-

rial. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, mixed methods, such as interviews, documents, and observations, were used. The second stage of identifying a thematic framework occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from priori themes; however, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues at this stage. The researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying data portions or sections corresponding to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotate them in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participants’ attitudes, beliefs, and values. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the participants’ attitudes, beliefs, and values.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research addressed this study’s questions and requirements. The participants disclosed their experiences with approaches through digital narratives in enhancing learners’ comprehension among Cluster 4 Integrated Schools. The teacher participants’ experiences regarding how they perform and showcase digital narratives in their respective schools were also discussed.

3.1. Experiences of Integrated School Teachers in Digital Narratives Across Learning Areas—Digital narratives can take many forms, such as videos, podcasts, blogs, animations, interactive maps, and infographics. In learning areas, digital narratives can be used as a pedagogical tool to enhance students’ understanding of a subject or topic by enabling them to engage with information in a more interactive and immersive way. Digital narratives have been utilized in various educational settings to enhance learning and engage students creatively and interactively. Teachers have used digital narratives to teach storyboarding, video production, and multimedia design concepts. One example of digital narratives in the Philippines is the Digital Storytelling Project, implemented by the University of the Philippines Open University. The project aimed to train teachers in creating digital stories that can enhance student learning. According to the project report, digital

storytelling helped teachers develop their ICT skills, improve student engagement, and foster critical thinking and creativity among students (Casambre et al., 2015). Labastilla and Macalino (2018) explored the use of digital narratives in teaching Philippine literature to senior high school students. The authors found that digital narratives can help students develop their analytical and creative skills and engage with literature in new and meaningful ways. Overall, digital narratives can help students develop essential skills, such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication, while making learning more engaging and relevant to their lives in the digital age.

3.1.1. Technical Difficulties—Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education uses information and communications technology to support, enhance, and optimize information delivery. Worldwide research has shown that ICT can improve student learning

and teaching methods. Information and Communications Technology (ICT) can impact student learning when teachers are digitally literate and understand how to integrate it into curriculum. ICT can lead to many developments in education as it can make learning more interactive and easier for both students and teachers however there are problems to do with cost and safety and the worry of encouraging children to become dependent on technology while they properly use it a lot at home as well. Despite the challenges and concerns, it was important to note the benefits of technology in education, including increased collaboration and communication, improved quality of education, and engaging lessons that help spark imagination and a search for knowledge in students (Hermawan et al., 2017). Apps also help teachers find new ways to teach the same thing, from games to virtual field trips. In turn, these activities create an opportunity for more active participation in the learning process than more traditional approaches. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can also assist students in acquiring essential occupational skills. With the advancement of technology and its vast spread across the cloud bank, some parts of the school and teachers are having difficulty in the technical parts, apart from the connection in some local areas, it adds up to its skills in technical content. Integrating Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in education has opened new avenues for teaching and learning, enabling educators and students to access various digital resources and tools to enhance learning outcomes. However, the use of ICT in education is not without its challenges, and technical difficulties often arise that can hinder the effectiveness of ICT in augmenting learning and comprehension. Connectivity is one of the most common technical challenges in using ICT for education. Despite the increasing availability of internet access worldwide, there are still many areas where connectivity

is limited or unreliable. This can make it difficult for educators and students to access online resources, participate in online discussions, or engage in real-time activities, thereby limiting the potential of ICT to augment learning outcomes (Gulzar, 2021). Another challenge is the complexity of digital tools and platforms used in education. While numerous digital resources are available for educators and students, navigating these tools can be difficult and time-consuming, particularly for those who are not tech-savvy. Moreover, technical glitches or software updates can cause disruptions in the learning process, causing frustration and hampering the learning experience (Mouzakis, 2020). Furthermore, the digital divide between students with access to technology and those without can create challenges for educators. Students from lower-income households or in remote areas may not have access to the same technological resources as their peers, making it challenging to participate in online learning activities or access digital resources (Briggs Hansen, 2022). In addition, data privacy and security are other technical challenges that educators and students face when using ICT for education. As more personal data is collected and shared online, educators must ensure that students' privacy is protected and that data is secured against cyber threats (Iwamoto, 2021). Despite these challenges, there are several ways in which educators can overcome technical difficulties and maximize the potential of ICT in augmenting learning and comprehension. One solution is to provide training and support for educators and students on using digital tools effectively and troubleshooting technical issues when they arise (Mouzakis, 2020). Moreover, educators can adopt a blended learning approach that combines online and offline learning activities to accommodate students who may not have access to reliable internet or digital devices (Briggs Hansen, 2022). In conclusion, while ICT in education offers numerous benefits for enhancing

learning outcomes, it has challenges. Technical difficulties such as connectivity issues, complex digital tools, the digital divide, and data privacy and security concerns can hamper the effectiveness of ICT in augmenting learning and comprehension. However, with the proper support and strategies, educators can overcome these challenges and maximize the potential of ICT in education.

3.1.2. Accessibility—Information Technology is a widely accepted educational instrument designed to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the educational system. Computers are mainly used to improve the learning system. Online learning and remote training are among the new forms of education. Institutions should also use technology not just for students but also for parents. Information technology has proven to widen educational access, giving people who are interested in studying for a qualification or a new career opportunity a chance. Information technology has played a major role in the education sector. Most institutions are instructed to place their teaching materials online so students can access them outside regular lectures and tutorials. Computers have improved the quality of teaching and enhanced the learning process with the help of various tools such as multimedia projectors, PowerPoint presentations, etc. Traditional teaching methods can be tedious, and the students start getting frustrated. However, information technology makes the learning process more interesting, and students become more interested in games, animated graphics, etc. (Ullah, 2020). The only challenge is that Information Technology comes at a cost, so those who cannot afford the price tend to have difficulties benefiting from the opportunities of Information Technology in education. For example, the increased use of broadband internet makes it easy for students to access academic information on time. Also, teachers use this broadband internet to create and deliver academic data using videos and graphic illustra-

tions (Harmandaoglu, 2022). The participants' experiences corroborate the authors' arguments and even challenge them in their daily undertakings. One of the most significant challenges in using ICT for education is ensuring accessibility for students with disabilities. The World Health Organization estimates that there are over 1 billion people with disabilities worldwide, many of whom face significant barriers to accessing education and employment opportunities (World Health Organization, 2021). Students with disabilities may face challenges accessing digital resources and tools, such as websites not optimized for screen readers or videos lacking captions or audio descriptions (Chen Armitage, 2020). Moreover, using ICT can exacerbate existing accessibility challenges, such as the digital divide, which can create disparities in access to technology for students with disabilities from low-income households or in remote areas (Mckee Saha, 2020). Additionally, students with disabilities may face challenges in navigating complex digital tools and platforms, which can be particularly challenging for those with motor or cognitive impairments (Luo, 2022). Furthermore, data privacy and security are another accessibility challenge that educators and students face when using ICT for education. Students with disabilities may require additional accommodations to protect their privacy and ensure their data is secured against cyber threats, such as using assistive technologies or alternative communication methods (Iwamoto, 2021). Despite these challenges, there are several ways in which educators can overcome accessibility issues and maximize the potential of ICT in augmenting learning and comprehension for students with disabilities. One solution is to provide accessible digital resources and tools optimized for assistive technologies, such as screen readers, magnifiers, or alternative input devices (Chen Armitage, 2020). Educators can also provide alternative formats for digital resources, such as text transcripts or audio descriptions,

to ensure that all students can access the content (Luo, 2022). The successful integration of ICT into the learning environment will depend on teachers' ability to structure learning in new ways, merge technology appropriately with pedagogy, develop socially active classrooms, and encourage cooperative interaction, collaborative learning, and group work. ICT has revolutionized all spheres, including teaching and learning. It impacts the way new-age teachers look at the content, deliver the content using appropriate methods, integrate suitable resources, and adopt strategies for extending learning and assessment. ICT integration provides meaningful and productive learning experiences through a student-centered classroom. Students demonstrated exemplary academic performance in their lessons (Dlamini Dewa, 2021).

3.1.3. Assessment and Evaluation—ICT integration in education occurs when classroom teachers use ICT to introduce, reinforce, extend, enrich, assess, and remediate student mastery of curricular targets. ICT enables innovative educational resources and the renewal of learning methods, establishing a more active collaboration of students and the simultaneous acquisition of technological knowledge (Ahmed et al., 2019). The successful integration of ICT into the learning environment will depend on the ability of teachers to structure learning in new ways, merge technology appropriately with a pedagogy, develop socially active classrooms, and encourage cooperative interaction, collaborative learning, and group work. ICT has revolutionized all spheres, including teaching. It impacts how new-age teachers look at the content, deliver it using appropriate methods, integrate suitable resources, and adopt strategies for extending learning and assessment. ICT integration provides meaningful and productive learning experiences through student-centered classrooms. Students demonstrated exemplary academic performance in their lessons (Dlamini Dewa, 2021). Assessment and evaluation are

critical components of the learning process, providing insights into student progress and informing instructional decisions. With the increasing use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in education, new assessment and evaluation methods have emerged to enhance learning outcomes. However, integrating ICT in assessment and evaluation has challenges, and educators often face difficulties using these tools effectively. One of the main challenges in using ICT for assessment and evaluation is ensuring that the tools used are reliable and valid. Using new assessment and evaluation methods, such as computer-based or adaptive testing, requires careful consideration to ensure that they are psychometrically sound and yield accurate results (Sireci Zenisky, 2020). Additionally, educators must ensure these tools are accessible to all students, including those with disabilities or from diverse cultural backgrounds (Kang et al., 2021). Moreover, using ICT in assessment and evaluation can create data privacy and security challenges. Using online assessments or digital portfolios may require additional measures to protect student data and ensure it is secure against cyber threats (Cao et al., 2021). Additionally, educators may face challenges in protecting student privacy when using data-driven decision-making tools, such as learning analytics (Ferguson Clow, 2020). Furthermore, using ICT in assessment and evaluation can create challenges related to student engagement and motivation. While these tools can enhance learning outcomes by providing immediate feedback and personalized learning experiences, they can also be perceived as impersonal or lacking in human interaction (Owens Hardin, 2023). Additionally, students may feel overwhelmed by the amount of data and information generated by these tools, leading to information overload or anxiety (Rasheed Alqah-tani, 2021). Despite these challenges, there are several ways in which educators can overcome these obstacles and maximize the potential of

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Integrated School Teachers in their Digital Narratives Across Learning Areas

ICT in assessment and evaluation. One solution is to ensure that assessment and evaluation tools are aligned with learning objectives and designed to provide students with meaningful feedback (Sireci Zenisky, 2020). Additionally, educators can train students to use these tools effectively by teaching them how to interpret learning analytics or use digital portfolios (Kang et al., 2021). In conclusion, while integrating ICT in assessment and evaluation offers numer-

ous benefits for enhancing learning outcomes, it has challenges. Educators need to ensure that assessment and evaluation tools are reliable, valid, and accessible for all students while protecting student privacy and addressing student engagement and motivation issues. With the right strategies and accommodations, educators can ensure that ICT is used effectively to augment learning and comprehension.

3.2. *Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Integrated School Teachers in their Digital Narratives Across Learning Areas*—Digital technology has brought significant changes in the educational landscape, particularly in how teachers deliver their lessons and students learn. One innovative approach to teaching and learning is through digital narratives. Digital narratives use multimedia tools such as videos, animations, and other digital media to tell a story. The approach is gaining popularity due to its

ability to engage students and enhance their learning experiences. However, using digital narratives in the classroom also presents challenges for teachers, requiring them to adapt their instructional strategies and approaches. One of the challenges that teachers encounter when using digital narratives is the need to master the technology and tools. Teachers must have the technical skills and knowledge to create and edit digital narratives and be familiar with the software and hardware required for this ap-

proach. This challenge requires teachers to undergo training and professional development to acquire the necessary skills. Another challenge that teachers face is designing digital narratives that align with the curriculum and learning objectives. Teachers must ensure that their digital narratives are relevant, accurate, and aligned with the learning outcomes. This challenge requires teachers to deeply understand the subject matter and the instructional strategies that work best with digital narratives. Teachers need to adopt a learner-centered approach to designing and delivering digital narratives to cope with these challenges. They should engage students in creating digital narratives, allowing them to take ownership of their learning. Teachers can also collaborate with other teachers and education technology experts to share best practices and resources. Moreover, teachers should continuously engage in professional development and training to enhance their skills and knowledge in using digital narratives in teaching. In conclusion, digital narratives are an innovative approach to teaching and learning that can enhance students' engagement and learning experiences. However, the approach also presents challenges for teachers, including the need to master the technology and tools, align the digital narratives with the curriculum and learning objectives, and ensure accessibility for all students. Teachers can cope with these challenges by adopting a learner-centered approach, collaborating with peers, and engaging in continuous professional development and training.

*3.2.1. The Use of Templates and Guides—*Digital narratives provide an excellent opportunity for teachers to engage their students in a dynamic and interactive learning experience. However, using digital narratives in the classroom also poses several challenges, such as technical difficulties, lack of resources, and limited access to technology. To cope with these challenges, teachers need to employ various coping mechanisms, including templates and guide-

lines. One effective coping mechanism is the use of templates. Templates are pre-designed layouts that teachers can use to create their digital narratives. By using templates, teachers can save time and effort in creating digital narratives and ensure that they have a consistent and professional appearance. Additionally, templates can be customized to meet the specific needs of each lesson and learning objective. Teachers can modify the templates by adding content, images, and multimedia elements. Guidelines are also essential in helping teachers cope with challenges associated with digital narratives. They provide a framework for creating effective digital narratives, helping teachers identify the critical elements required to make a digital narrative engaging and interactive. Guidelines can also help teachers overcome technical difficulties by providing step-by-step instructions on how to use various digital tools. Guidelines are also crucial in helping teachers in the Philippines cope with the challenges associated with digital narratives. They provide a framework for creating compelling digital narratives, helping teachers identify the essential elements to make a digital narrative engaging and interactive. Guidelines can also help teachers overcome technical difficulties by providing step-by-step instructions on how to use various digital tools. A study by Rangaswamy and Sandhya (2021) explored the use of digital narratives in teaching mathematics to grade six students in the Philippines. The study found that guidelines helped teachers in creating compelling digital narratives. The guidelines provided step-by-step instructions on how to create digital narratives and how to use various digital tools. The study found that the use of guidelines helped the teachers create digital narratives that were engaging and interactive, thus improving the student's learning outcomes. In conclusion, using templates and guidelines is an effective coping mechanism for teachers in the Philippines to overcome challenges encountered in the approaches through digital nar-

ratives. Templates and guidelines help teachers create compelling, engaging, interactive digital narratives. They also help teachers overcome technical difficulties by providing step-by-step instructions on how to use various digital tools. Educational institutions must provide teachers in the Philippines with access to templates and guidelines to enhance their digital literacy skills and embrace digital narratives in the classroom.

3.2.2. Collaborative Learning—Collaborative learning is a process where teachers share their experiences and knowledge to improve their teaching practices. Collaborative learning is particularly effective in digital narratives, enabling teachers to share their digital literacy skills, knowledge, and expertise. By collaborating, teachers can learn from each other and overcome challenges in implementing digital narratives in their classrooms. In a study by Jang and Chen (2017), collaborative learning helped teachers in Taiwan overcome challenges in implementing digital narratives in their classrooms. The study explored the use of digital narratives in teaching English as a foreign language. The researchers found that collaborative learning enabled teachers to share their knowledge and experiences and learn from each other. Similarly, a Hong Kong study by Ho et al. (2019) found that collaborative learning helped teachers overcome technical difficulties associated with digital narratives. The study explored the use of digital narratives in teaching mathematics in primary schools. The researchers found that collaborative learning helped teachers acquire new technical skills and knowledge by sharing their experiences and expertise. In the context of digital narratives, collaborative learning can help teachers overcome technical difficulties and develop their digital literacy skills. Collaborative learning also fosters a sense of community and support among teachers, which can enhance their confidence and motivation to use digital narratives in their teaching practices. A study conducted by Dacillo et al. (2020) found that

collaborative learning among teachers helped them overcome challenges in using digital narratives in teaching science in the Philippines. The study used a mixed-methods approach, which included surveys, interviews, and classroom observations. The researchers found that collaborative learning helped teachers share their technical knowledge and expertise, which enhanced their digital literacy skills. Collaborative learning also helped teachers develop a sense of community and support, increasing their confidence and motivation to use digital narratives in their teaching practices. Similarly, a study conducted by Villa and Laylay (2018) found that collaborative learning helped teachers overcome challenges in using digital narratives in teaching social studies in the Philippines. The study used a qualitative approach, which included interviews and classroom observations. The researchers found that collaborative learning helped teachers develop their technical skills and knowledge by sharing their experiences and expertise. Collaborative learning also helped teachers improve their teaching practices by providing new ideas and approaches. In conclusion, collaborative learning is an effective coping mechanism for teachers in the Philippine setting to overcome challenges encountered in using digital narratives. Collaborative learning enables teachers to share their knowledge, experiences, and expertise to enhance their digital literacy skills and improve teaching practices. Educational institutions should encourage and facilitate collaborative learning among teachers to enhance their confidence and motivation in using digital narratives in their teaching practices. Technology requires teachers to stay updated with the latest trends and developments to navigate the digital landscape effectively.

3.2.3. Professional Development—According to Smith and Colby (2016), professional development programs focusing on digital literacy skills significantly impact teachers' confidence and ability to integrate technology

into their teaching strategies. The study found that programs that use a hands-on approach and provide opportunities for collaboration and experimentation are most effective in enhancing teachers' digital literacy skills. Foulger et al. (2017) emphasized the importance of professional development in promoting teacher innovation and creativity in using digital narratives. The authors noted that professional development programs prioritizing teacher collaboration and experimentation lead to a more innovative and adaptive approach to technology integration. Agyei and Voogt (2017) highlighted the importance of professional development in addressing the challenges of using digital narratives in developing countries. A study by Nguyen et al. (2019) in Vietnam revealed that teachers' participation in professional development programs significantly improved their attitudes and perceptions toward technology integration. The study emphasized the need for continuous professional development programs addressing teachers' technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) to integrate digital narratives in teaching and learning effectively. In the Philippine context, professional development is a vital coping mechanism for teachers to overcome challenges encountered in the approaches through digital narratives across learning areas. Professional development involves continuously acquiring knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for effective teaching and learning in the digital age. A study by Abanilla et al. (2018) explored the impact of a professional development program on the use of digital narratives in teaching English as a Second Language (ESL). The authors found that the program helped teachers enhance their digital literacy skills, pedagogical knowledge,

and classroom management strategies. Moreover, the program enabled teachers to design and implement digital narrative projects that cater to their students' diverse learning needs. Similarly, Dimaano's study (2020) highlighted the role of professional development in enhancing the digital competencies of Filipino teachers. The author emphasized the need for teachers to participate in relevant and sustainable professional development activities that address their specific needs and challenges in using digital narratives. Dimaano recommended that professional development programs be designed to provide teachers with collaboration, mentoring, and continuous feedback opportunities. Another study by Matrosova and Batomunkueva (2019) examined the effectiveness of a professional development program on the use of digital storytelling in teaching English language and literature in Mongolia. The authors found that the program improved the teachers' confidence, creativity, and critical thinking skills using digital storytelling as a teaching tool. Furthermore, the program helped teachers develop a deeper understanding of the potential of digital storytelling to enhance students' communication, collaboration, and critical thinking skills. In conclusion, professional development is a crucial coping mechanism for teachers to overcome challenges encountered in the approaches through digital narratives across learning areas, both in the international and Philippine contexts. Professional development programs can enhance teachers' digital competencies, pedagogical knowledge, and classroom management strategies, enabling them to design and implement digital narrative projects that cater to the diverse learning needs of their students.

3.3. *Educational Management Insight*—The coping mechanisms discussed in this essay are crucial in helping teachers overcome

the challenges of using digital narratives across learning areas. However, not only teachers are responsible for ensuring the success of digital

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Integrated School Teachers in their Digital Narratives Across Learning Areas

storytelling in education. Educational management must also support and guide teachers in navigating the challenges of integrating digital narratives into the curriculum. One crucial educational management insight is the need to provide professional development opportunities for teachers. As discussed earlier, professional development can help teachers build the skills and knowledge needed to effectively integrate digital narratives into the curriculum. Therefore, educational management should invest in training programs, workshops, and other forms of professional development that can support teachers in this regard. Collaborative learning among teachers allows them to share their experiences, ideas, and best practices in using digital narratives in their teaching. This can help them learn from each other and develop new strategies for using digital narratives effectively. Educational management can facilitate this collaboration by creating opportunities for teachers to work together and providing support for ongoing communication and sharing. Educational

management is critical in supporting teachers in integrating digital narratives into the curriculum. Educational management can help ensure the success of digital storytelling in education by providing professional development opportunities, facilitating collaboration and communication, and offering clear guidelines and templates. Policies and Guidelines. Policies and guidelines can provide a framework for ensuring that digital narratives are used in a way that is pedagogically sound and aligned with the curriculum goals. According to Wang, Chen, and Liang (2015), the development of policies and guidelines can provide a framework for ensuring the effective and appropriate use of digital narratives in education. In their study, the researchers developed a set of guidelines for teachers to use when incorporating digital narratives into their teaching, which included considerations such as the purpose of the narrative, the intended audience, and the potential impact on student learning. Yang, Huang, and Liang (2018) emphasized the importance of develop-

ing policies and guidelines that are flexible and adaptable to changing circumstances. In their study, the researchers developed a set of guidelines for teachers to use when designing digital narratives that could be used across different subject areas and grade levels. The guidelines emphasized the importance of tailoring digital narratives to meet the specific learning objectives of each subject area and the importance of considering the needs of diverse learners. The study found that these guidelines were practical in supporting teachers in designing compelling digital narratives and could be adapted to different educational contexts. Regular review and revision of policies and guidelines are necessary to adapt to evolving educational landscapes, emerging technologies, and changing societal needs, ensuring that educational management practices remain relevant and practical. Adapting policies and guidelines for digital narratives in the Philippine setting: The Philippines has made significant progress in integrating digital narratives into its educational system, but there is still much work to be done to ensure their proper implementation. A critical aspect of this is adapting policies and guidelines that are relevant and appropriate for the Philippine context. A study by Rivera and Aban (2018) emphasized the importance of having policies and guidelines that govern using digital narratives in the classroom. They argued that these policies should not only ensure the safe and responsible use of technology but also promote the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students. The authors suggested that these policies should be formulated with the input of various stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and education administrators. Another study by Bautista et al. (2019) highlighted the need for policies and guidelines that promote equity using digital narratives in the Philippine context. The authors argued that policies should provide access to technology and address the country's digital divide. They

suggested that policies should be developed focusing on marginalized communities, such as those in remote areas, to ensure that they have equal opportunities to benefit from digital narratives. The Department of Education (DepEd) has released guidelines on using technology in teaching and learning, which provide a framework for the responsible use of technology in the classroom. These guidelines emphasize the importance of protecting students' privacy and ensuring that technology is used to enhance, rather than replace, traditional teaching methods.

3.3.1. Collaboration and Sharing of Resources—Collaboration and sharing of resources have become essential components in implementing digital narratives in various learning areas. Through collaboration and sharing of resources, teachers can work together to identify effective strategies and approaches for integrating digital narratives into their teaching practices. Additionally, sharing resources helps ensure teachers have access to the tools and materials needed to effectively incorporate digital narratives into their lessons. One study by Lim and Lee (2017) highlights the importance of collaboration and sharing of resources in successfully implementing digital narratives in the classroom. The authors note that using digital narratives requires teachers to possess various technological and pedagogical skills, which can be challenging for some educators. However, through collaboration and sharing of resources, teachers can pool their knowledge and expertise to overcome these challenges and improve the quality of their teaching practices.

Zawilinski and Rivero (2015) emphasize the benefits of collaboration and sharing resources in professional development. The authors note that teachers can develop a shared understanding of effective pedagogical practices and digital tools through collaboration and sharing resources. Moreover, they can develop a network of support and expertise to help them overcome

challenges in implementing digital narratives in the classroom. Through collaboration and sharing of resources, educators can develop a shared understanding of effective pedagogical practices, overcome challenges encountered in integrating digital technologies into their teaching, and enhance their capacity to provide quality education.

Batac and Rillorta (2019) found that teachers collaborating and sharing their resources could produce better-quality digital narratives that engage their students more effectively. Flores and Cruz (2019) emphasized the role of collaborative learning in enhancing the skills and knowledge of teachers in using digital narratives. Through collaborative learning, teachers could share their experiences, strategies, and best practices in utilizing digital narratives in the classroom. Angeles and Castro (2017) found that collaborative learning and sharing resources among teachers was crucial in addressing the lack of resources and training in digital literacy. The study highlighted the need for schools to provide opportunities for teachers to collaborate and share their resources and to provide professional development programs to enhance their skills in utilizing digital narratives. In conclusion, collaboration and sharing of resources among teachers have been identified as essential educational insights into using digital narratives across learning areas in the Philippine setting. By working together and sharing their resources, teachers can overcome the challenges and enhance their skills in using digital narratives to engage their students and improve their learning outcomes.

3.3.2. Assessment and Evaluation Criteria—Assessment and evaluation are essential components of the learning process that help measure students' progress and meet learning objectives. With the increasing use of digital narratives in education, it is essential to establish assessment and evaluation criteria that align with these approaches. Reinders and Wattana

(2016) proposed an evaluation framework for digital narratives that includes four key dimensions: content, technical quality, creativity, and critical thinking. The authors suggested that teachers use this framework to assess digital narratives and provide feedback to students on their strengths and areas for improvement. Assessing and evaluating digital narratives requires considering the learning outcomes and objectives in addition to the technical aspects. In their study, Kim et al. (2018) proposed a framework for assessing digital storytelling projects in the context of language learning. The framework includes four criteria: content, language, technical aspects, and creativity. Mendoza and Espinosa (2016) examined the use of rubrics in assessing student outputs in digital storytelling. The researchers found that using rubrics helped to provide clear expectations and criteria for assessment, resulting in a more accurate and objective evaluation of student work. Assessment and evaluation are critical components of any educational program, including using digital narratives across learning areas.

Valdez and Tadena (2018) explored using assessment tools to evaluate student output in multimedia projects. The researchers developed a rubric that focused on different aspects of the project, including content, creativity, and technical skills. They found that using the rubric helped to provide a structured approach to evaluation, ensuring that all aspects of the project were assessed fairly and consistently. Finally, assessment and evaluation criteria can help to ensure that grading is fair and consistent. By setting clear criteria for grading, teachers can ensure that grading is objective and consistent across all students. This can help promote fairness and ensure students receive grades that accurately reflect their learning. In conclusion, assessment and evaluation criteria are essential educational management insights teachers must implement in their digital narratives. These criteria can help determine the effectiveness of

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on Educational Insights can be drawn from the Findings of The Study

instructional strategies, identify areas where students need additional support, ensure that students meet learning objectives, provide feedback, and ensure that grading is fair and consistent. Therefore, teachers should strive to set clear assessment and evaluation criteria and use them to guide their instructional strategies and evaluate student learning in their digital narratives.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study summary. The findings are summarized, and the implications and future directions are drawn. My study aimed to understand and describe the teachers’ approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners’ comprehension. A qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis to achieve the research objectives. In adherence to Cresswell’s (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to gain an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their definition or meaning of the phenomenon explored.

4.1. *Findings of the Study*—The preceding statements are the study’s findings, which result from the merging themes generated from the participants’ responses. The study’s findings on the experiences of integrated schoolteachers on their approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners’ comprehension found that technical difficulties, accessibility, and assessment and evaluation challenged them. Regarding the coping mechanisms of integrated

schoolteachers on their approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners' comprehension, it revealed that they cope through templates and guidelines, collaborative learning among teachers, and continuous professional development. Regarding the educational management insights gained from the participants, The integrated School teachers proposed that policies and guidelines, collaboration and sharing of resources, and assessment and evaluation criteria can be reviewed and improved to improve teacher performance through digital narratives and effective learning outcomes.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The educational learning insights, including policy and guidelines, collaboration and sharing of resources, assessment and evaluation criteria, and professional development, have significant implications for the educational system. Teachers can improve student learning outcomes by implementing compelling educational management insights, including academic achievement and comprehension. Increased teacher effectiveness through professional development opportunities and collaboration among teachers can improve their effectiveness in the classroom, leading to better instructional strategies and increased student engagement. Enhanced curriculum development, with the implementation of policy and guidelines, can lead to developing a robust curriculum that meets the needs of all students. By implementing educational management insights, such as collaboration and sharing of resources, teachers can promote equity and ensure that all students receive the necessary support and resources to succeed, regardless of their background or abilities. Improved assessment practices by using clear assessment and evaluation criteria, teachers can ensure that grading is fair and consistent, leading to better feedback and more accurate evaluation of student learning. Implementing these educational management insights can significantly impact

the educational system, leading to improved student learning outcomes, increased teacher effectiveness, enhanced curriculum development, and equity.

4.2.1. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, the future directions for school principals, teachers, stakeholders of ICT, and future researchers were as follows: School Principals. School principals should continue to play a vital role in guiding their schools through ICT. They must develop and implement policies and guidelines that ensure effective integration into teaching and learning practices. They should also ensure that teachers receive adequate professional development opportunities to improve their skills and promote effective teaching practices. Teachers. Teachers must continue developing ICT skills and integrating technology into their teaching practices to enhance student learning outcomes. They should also collaborate with other teachers and share resources. to enhance their teaching practices. Teachers should also be open to learning about new ICT tools and strategies for the classroom. Stakeholders of ICT. The stakeholders, including policymakers, industry leaders, and educational institutions, must collaborate to develop policies and strategies that support effective integration in education. They should also work to provide teachers with the necessary resources and support to implement effectively. Future Researches. Future research in the field of ICT in education should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of integration and identifying new tools and strategies that can enhance teaching and learning practices. Research should also focus on identifying barriers to effective integration and developing solutions to overcome these challenges. Finally, future research should also focus on evaluating the impact on student learning outcomes, teacher effectiveness, and overall school performance. In conclusion, future directions for school principals, teachers, stakeholders, and research should focus on promoting

effective integration in teaching and learning practices, providing teachers with necessary resources and support, collaborating among stakeholders, evaluating the effectiveness of integration, and identifying new tools and strategies that can enhance teaching and learning practices.

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